

MIMS 2+ : Applications and Discussions

A continuing internal dialogue about the use of the MIMS theory with particular application to discussion of Thomas Edison, Business, Mysticism, Conspiracy Theories, Innovation, and Personal Finance Management

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ABSTRACT

Continuing our philosophical inquiry into the Membranous Interface of the Material and Spiritual¹ realms, the author here wishes to have a loose fit dialogue on the subject. This is not the promised rigorous analysis for Dual Layer Economics, the theory is not ready for that. In part 1.0 we launched the theory, and DLE, with the use of two cases only: a grocery store visit, and cryptocurrency (or bitcoin) mining. We will not in this paper revisit the diagram, but proceed to use the yang over yin over yang layering *assumptively*. We will, however, revisit the *F*, *N*, and *P* powers from Figure 3 of that paper repeatedly. The reader should familiarize themselves with this diagram thoroughly before continuing.

This paper will cover 2.0, 2.1, 2.2, etc. to 2.5. It may be that particular returns to these will occur, and dotting the cases will enable some specificity and detail, as there are large MIMS (such as the Federal Reserve), and small MIMS (such as your credit card statement). How these affect larger issues in our lives is not at all clear, and yet it has been a study of the Chinese Sciences for thousands of years, and a point of continual study in Operations Research for 75 years, with the most rapid expansive progress being in the 1960's. As for PEMC, the first few cases of a mimsical interaction on record are Isacc Newton's optics experiments, Benjamin Franklin's kite experiment, Volta's batteries, Faraday's motor, Tesla's motor, and - unfortunately - Oppenheimer and the entire government's atomic and subsequent Hydrogen Bomb experiments. The stakes are ever increasing, and the author will, in this paper, even propose a model to describe progress and anti-progress in an *Innovation Curve*. The question is can we see overlap with any other mimsy analysis?

Keywords: MIMS - business - Tesla - Edison - Westinghouse - Newton - Innovation - Mysticism

Introduction

As the reader may recall, there is some question put forward - even as early as the Birkeland Polyphase Superweb² and Mars³ papers - which nags upon the author as it touches the subject of futurism and innovation. Can we, in fact “pull down” data from the ‘future’; engineer as it were a way to pre-vision ideas as easily as a science fiction writer or artist, which then become actionable innovation well ahead of the expected trajectory? The author again proposes, for example, that mankind was not ready for powered flight and to master the wings and principles of flight (*P power*), and yet the spirit was ready and able. So in 1783 Ed Yost invented the hot air balloon⁴, and man began to ‘fly’. This led to the zeppelin and other basically powered flights, as well as gliding, parachuting, etc. It simply was not time yet for mankind to take flight in aeroplanes. Yet, it was done. Something moved through a form of active osmosis into the real domain, and mankind flew more than 100 years ahead of actual powered flight.

Back to the Birkeland Polyphase Superweb... the concepts the author shared are based upon current active sciences in plasma physics, computing, aerospace, IT/data and medicine, and this leads to many ‘speculations’ which will likely come to pass, if mankind survives World War 3. However, the question is, do we have to wait for the innovation, and are there economic rewards (or indeed maybe punishments⁵), to fast-forwarding development? For example, if we shouldn’t be capable of terraforming Mars for 200 years, what if we could do it in 120, or 80? Would it be worth the *bending* and leveraging... or like the USSR Space Shuttle program become a “bridge too far”⁶?

Moreover, and more to the point as far as the author’s think tank AIMtm is concerned: is it scalable? Is it representative of a data-driven pathway that can make trendline projections based upon AI-run mimsical analysis, of areas to innovate in order to “bridge the gaps”? Normally, we wait for a genius like Tesla to make the Alternating Current world possible. But what if right from the moment that Faraday comes up with the AC motor, one could bridge the gap “early”? Would one even know? Probably not. But the author contends it’d be worth a fortune.

Such is the first case we shall discuss, the curious reality of Mr. Thomas Edison, “inventor” of the light bulb.

2.0 The Man Who Turned On the World

Thomas Edison was an American hero, and for over 100 years people knew it. However, recently the internet’s discovery of Nikola Tesla (especially after the movie “The Prestige”) led to scrutiny of the man, until he was portrayed accurately but rather ignobly in “The Current War” by actor Benedict Cumberbatch. While it is true he was a ruthless capitalist, and went so far as to invent the electric chair to blame on AC, it is understandable now that he was desperate to save his company from ruin. Unethical, but understandable. He

²

https://www.academia.edu/38560727/Birkeland_Polyphase_Superweb_A_Proposition_for_the_Future_Betterment_of_Mankind_global_defense_interconnection_and_unlimited_power

³

https://www.academia.edu/38759087/Opinion_Mars_Mission_Planning_is_Premature_Expensive_and_likely_Short_Sighted

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hot-air_balloon

⁵ Consider the odd case of “Space Energy” company, and how the entrepreneur Peter Sage went from a probable \$28 billion company, to jail for an unrelated - and maybe (if conspiracies are true) setup that involved Hewlett Packard and corrupt UK judges. <https://www.petersage.com/spaceenergy>, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cT_xNON1_bA vs https://www.theregister.com/2017/02/23/peter_sage_42000_hpe_servers_alleged_fraud_space_energy/

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XLOCQw5s9Uw>

had done something rather spectacular (he and his aides), and naturally wanted to cash in. If only he had paid Mr. Tesla \$50,000 for his work, maybe he could have had it all. Nevertheless, few people can see into the future, and he made these grave mistakes, and went on to invent many other genius ideas to which we owe him credit (such as motion pictures, and the phonograph, etc.; see section 2.1)⁷

One thing he did not invent, technically, is the light bulb.⁸ What he did was figure out how to make incandescence via filament work with DC current, and invent the means of inserting it into the socket for DC power delivery.⁹ Many of his standards were abandoned or modified later... but when he turned on the world to electric lighting¹⁰, he opened up people to the *F* power - the PEM force - as no one in the world ever had or has since. People everywhere became **enlightened**, literally, almost as if they had a moment of satori¹¹. Let us hear now, in his own words, the struggle it was to achieve this great feat, this herculean effort which made him the modern Prometheus:

“No one, including Edison, ever counted the number of experimental lamps that they made. There were hundreds of experiments before he developed the bamboo lamp. And many additional experiments before the lamps were adequate for commercial production. In a letter to Edison in spring 1884, Francis Upton noted that the [lamp factory had conducted 2,774 experiments](#)¹² (presumably since it had started operations in October 1881).

The source of the story about Edison trying thousands of experiments or materials is probably an 1890 interview in *Harper's Monthly Magazine*:

*"I speak without exaggeration when I say that I have constructed three thousand different theories in connection with the electric light, each one of them reasonable and apparently to be true. Yet only in two cases did my experiments prove the truth of my theory. My chief difficulty, as perhaps you know, was in constructing the carbon filament, the incandescence of which is the source of the light. Every quarter of the globe was ransacked by my agents, and all sorts of the queerest materials were used, until finally the shred of bamboo now utilized was settled upon. Even now, Mr. Edison continued, 'I am still at work nearly every day on the lamp, and quite lately I have devised a method of supplying sufficient current to fifteen lamps with one horse-power. Formerly ten lamps per horse-power was the extreme limit.'"*¹³

And he is to have said, *"I didn't fail 1,000 times. The light bulb was an invention with 1,000 steps."*

Setting aside the whether or not we can engineer the future now, if we knew that this invention was bound to succeed - fated as it were - it was absolutely, categorically, undeniably true that it should, and that be it 1,000 or 100,000 trials, it would have been worth it. Imagine life without computers, modern phones, traffic lights, indoor lighting (how would modern airplanes work?), and lighted hospitals. How would you enjoy getting surgery by candlelight? With no heart rhythm screens or bright lights to illuminate your open chest? By modern standards medicine was in the dark ages at the time Edison figured out incandescence in 1880. Think of that:

⁷ There is a museum for him where he lived briefly in Louisville, KY, near the author which displays some of his authentic inventions. They are nevertheless impressive.

⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electric_light

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Edison_screw

¹⁰ <https://worldsfairchicago1893.com/tag/thomas-edison/>

¹¹ For once, magic was real. "Satori (悟り) is a Japanese Buddhist term for awakening, "comprehension; understanding". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Satori>

¹² <http://edison.rutgers.edu/NamesSearch/SingleDoc.php?DocId=D8429ZAO>

¹³ <https://edison.rutgers.edu/newsletter9.html>

1880. Spectroscopy had been in existence since 1848. The first American railroad was laid in 1828. That meant that cars were lit by oil and flammables were in ready supply on every carriage!

So we must conclude that if it were theoretically possible to push for a world changing invention, and to handle the “lightning in a bottle” it represents and such that no one could “steal the thunder”. Then it would be worth almost every dollar in present existence to have such a method, and promote a line of scientific inquiry and data analytics into this effect.

Think of it another way: in the time of Jesus or Moses, the secrets of the first Egyptians who designed the wondrous feats of engineering at Giza and Karnak were long gone. It was an age of superstition and backwardness. People literally chose a murderer over an innocent man¹⁴, and then had Yeshua tortured brutally, and put on display next to thieves whose crimes also did not necessarily deserve crucifixion. In such a time, if a man proposed an embetterment of electric lighting, having (let’s propose) seen the Crooke’s tubes on the temple at Dendera and been enlightened like a Nikola Tesla, and set about to re-invent it... what would happen?

Comparative Analysis of Dendera Lights to Cathode Ray Tube

Figure 1 - Dendera CRT's; powered by electric fields of the Giza Power Plant¹⁵; credit: AfricanCreationEnergy¹⁶

At first his friends and family would laugh. Local authorities would bemuse themselves. Thieves would set about to steal his supplies or con him out of new materials in fake trades. Promises of the secrets of Atlantis would be sold, and he could even be set up for an alley murder. The “town loon” he would be named. If

¹⁴ Barabas

¹⁵ By engineer Chris Dunn

¹⁶ <http://africancreationenergy.blogspot.com/2015/11/egyptian-light-bulb-plausible.html>

he set about to systematically do the work, after 20 or 30 failures he'd be labeled a crank. After 100 a threat to the youth's sanity. At 200 or 300 he would be put on trial for fraud (like Peter Sage?) and burned perhaps as a sorcerer. Or like Socrates made to drink the hemlock or nightshade, wolf's bane, etc.

Even in the 1300's AD chances are good he could secure a job if he could make up fake scientific concepts to sell to greedy, stupid, vain princes in promise of immortality and infinite power¹⁷. But it would not have lasted 1,000 to 3,000 trials, in this author's opinion.

What type of MIMS enable Thomas A. Edison to achieve this feat? Did he, as Tesla did, simply envision it? Clearly not, for Nikola Tesla built his machine from his vision¹⁸ and it worked as he imagined it with few modifications.

Thomas Edison used the best MIMS - objectively speaking - ever created: the scientific method.

Figure 2 - the MIMS known as the Scientific Method; credit: Lumenlearning.com¹⁹

The scientific method is a method harkening back to the early concepts of Socrates' form of inquiry. A special type of precision questioning and answering method,

¹⁷ Ala John Dee, etc.

¹⁸ According to his autobiography

¹⁹

<https://courses.lumenlearning.com/introchem/chapter/the-scientific-method/#:~:text=The%20scientific%20method%20was%20used.inductive%20methods%20for%20scientific%20inquiry.>

one might say²⁰. It was known to be particularly maddening to all other philosophers and passersby whom he would harass with his smelly pits and quick wits.

Technically speaking though it was Sir Francis Bacon who set up the inductive methods of true scientific inquiry in 1605, although it was probably based upon Rober Bacon’s method in the 1200’s. Earlier scientists must have existed, but they aren’t as well documented, or had flaws in their system.²¹

Why is this MIMS so ‘arbitrarily’ powerful? Is it the harmonics created by the 10 steps? Is it the

potentiality for both infinite inquiry (such as finding the light bulb well beyond reasonableness to give up), while also having a definite end? This reminds the author of the 11-linked chain of the MIMS of Karma (12 for the Buddha, but it was an entire circle²²) which he documented elsewhere. In such a system there is repetition of reality in that actions lead inexorably to results, due to the *P* power of the Law of Causality.

Figure 3 - “The implied 11” factors of the 12 linked chain of causation; credit: author

(2006)

Please note that this acts as the “warp” to the “weft” of the 12 link chain of the Buddha.

It is an early mimesque model, but it is, perhaps, really several MIMS at interplay through the discussion of psychology and biology, both governed primarily by the *P* power.

²⁰ <https://sourcesofinsight.com/precision-questions-and-precision-answers/>

²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_scientific_method

²² https://encyclopediaofbuddhism.org/wiki/Twelve_links_of_dependent_origination

This then is our own first hypothesis to the secret of the MIMS that can shake the world by bringing the future to the now: use the scientific method, and in particular **it must contain the infinite and the finite** (or definite²³). (I)

2.1 Mind Your Own Business

One of the most key entrepreneurial axioms is to MYOB²⁴. Of course, this means to consider the “bottom line”²⁵ but also to literally keep your F.O.C.U.S.²⁶ When people get entangled in interpersonal competition instead of business competition, they begin to play “follow the follower,” and they “leave the field” to go “chase the birds.”²⁷ This leads to disastrous business failings.²⁸

But why is business something Ayn Rand considered so essential, so Holy (in a way)? Is it the service a business renders? Is it the way entrepreneurship frees families from poverty? Is it the way business, particularly small and medium sized businesses, builds the nation? Or is it something more essential than this? Is it, perhaps as she felt and expressed through her timeless character John Galt, that business is the ultimate material expression of man’s innate value and spiritual offering to the world, which others can *directly* relate to, use, benefit from, and for which he is also rewarded, and not punished, or promised punishment? Is business²⁹ a MIMS?

Let us revisit the lives of the three men mentioned earlier (one by proxy) in “the Current War”:

❖ Thomas A. Edison:

- Invented the incandescent light bulb, phonograph, electric chair, film, kinoscope, movie camera, phonographic cylinder (storage medium), DC power distribution, mimeograph, electric pen, vitascope, phonomotor, vacuum diode, quadruplex telegraph, tasimeter, and kinetophone
- Net Worth: \$170 million in 2021 adjusted for inflation³⁰
- Died aged 84, 6 kids³¹ from 1 marriage
- Awards: honorary PhD from Union College (1878), Officer of the Legion of Honor (1881), Chevalier (1879), Commander of the Legion (1889), Matteucci Medal (1890), John Scott Medal (1889), Edward Longstreth Medal (1899), honorable Consulting engineer at Exposition World’s Fair (1904), AAES John Fritz Medal (1908), Franklin Medal (1915), Navy Distinguish Service Medal (1920), AIEE first Edison Medal (1923), National Academy of Sciences (1927), Congressional Gold Medal (1928), National Inventors Day, Edison’s birthday starting 1983, New

²³ Although notice how many ‘definite’ laws of physics and constants turn out to only be parts of the answer, or steps on the way to the truth?

²⁴ <https://www.businessmagazinegainesville.com/myob-mind-business/>

²⁵ Be, in particular, a profit first driven company. Many criticize this mentality but they should remember Jesus’ cryptic or mystical warning, “For whoever has, to him shall more be given, and he shall have an abundance; but whoever does not have, even what he has shall be taken away from him.” Matthew 5:30

²⁶ Follow One Course Until Successful. “The Midas Touch,” D. Trump & R. Kiyosaki, 2011

²⁷ 13 That same day Jesus went out of the house and sat by the lake. 2 Such large crowds gathered around him that he got into a boat and sat in it, while all the people stood on the shore. 3 Then he told them many things in parables, saying: “A farmer went out to sow his seed. 4 As he was scattering the seed, some fell along the path, and the birds came and ate it up. 5 Some fell on rocky places, where it did not have much soil. It sprang up quickly, because the soil was shallow. 6 But when the sun came up, the plants were scorched, and they withered because they had no root. 7 Other seed fell among thorns, which grew up and choked the plants. 8 Still other seed fell on good soil, where it produced a crop—a hundred, sixty or thirty times what was sown. 9 Whoever has ears, let them hear.” Matthew 13:1-9

²⁸ <https://www.indy100.com/news/jeff-bezos-space-flight-wally-funk-review-b1888710>

²⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business_history

³⁰ <https://www.forbes.com/forbes/2002/1223/258.html?sh=64efb8e666e6>

³¹ <https://www.wealthypersons.com/thomas-edison-net-worth-2020-2021/>

Jersey Hall of Fame (2008), Technical Grammy Award (2010), Entrepreneurial Wall of Fame (2011)

➤ Patents: 1,093³²

❖ Nikola Tesla:

➤ Invented the induction motor, remote control, tesla coil, 3-phase AC power, Tesla turbine, Tesla valve, teleforce, robots, telegeodynamics, wireless communications, violet ray, neon lamp, and vacuum variable capacitor. He also predicted the atomic bomb, intercontinental missiles, and artificial intelligence in his autobiography.³³

➤ Net worth: \$100³⁴

➤ Died aged 86, 0 kids³⁵ or marriages.

➤ Awards: Order of St. Sava, II Class, Government of Serbia (1892), Elliott Cresson Medal (1894), Order of Prince Danilo I (1895), Edison Medal (1916), Order of St. Sava, I Class, Government of Yugoslavia (1926), Order of the Yugoslav Crown (1931), John Scott Medal (1934), Order of the White Eagle, I Class, Government of Yugoslavia (1936), Order of the White Lion, I Class, Government of Czechoslovakia (1937), University of Paris Medal (1937), The Medal of the University St Clement of Ochrida, Sofia, Bulgaria (1939)³⁶

➤ Patents: 278-300

❖ George Westinghouse:

➤ Invented the railway air brake; smart enough to hire Tesla to make AC motors and electrical systems

➤ Net worth: \$1.2 billion³⁷

➤ Died aged 67, 1 child by 1 marriage³⁸

➤ Awards: John Fritz Medal (1906), and IEEE Edison Medal (1911)

Every person's destiny is different, and all three men are to be commended. But if one had to choose any of the three lives it would - hands down - have to be Thomas A. Edison. Yet all were touched with myriad forms of wealth and recognition by the successful use of the PEM, and its employment to do work. So why is it that, despite there being clear wealth tied to the PEMF, Tesla alone was unable to turn this into a lifetime of furthering achievement and wealth? How is it that the man who held the patent to the world's second greatest³⁹ invention of all time, ended up with \$100 at death?

What is the secret of business, as it relates to the successful mediation of the *F*, *P*, and *N* powers?

³² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Edison

³³ <https://www.mcnabb.com/music/tesla/bio.pdf> pp17-22

³⁴ "The generally accepted story states that Westinghouse paid Tesla around \$60,000 for his patents for AC motors and generators, that's roughly the equivalent of \$1.4 million in today's dollars. Tesla was also given a \$2000 a month salary to work for Westinghouse, the equivalent of \$48,000 per month today."

<https://geekhistory.com/content/george-westinghouse-used-tesla-power-defeat-edison-currents-war>

³⁵ <https://www.celebritynetworth.com/richest-celebrities/authors/nikola-tesla-net-worth/>

³⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nikola_Tesla

³⁷ <https://www.archbridgeinstitute.org/2019/02/27/george-westinghouse-servant-leader-inventor-captain-of-industry>.

³⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/George_Westinghouse

³⁹ Or third, depending on where you put fractional reserve lending. Depending on your definition of great.

This may be one of the most challenging paradoxes of MIMS, especially given as the author has noted elsewhere⁴⁰, that the equation for power in business is different than in the laws of physics. It is inverted.

But if Edison and Westinghouse could mediate this inversion, then why could not Tesla? Or if Tesla was simply terrible with money, why wasn't the wealth of the attraction of females and admiring disciples heaped upon him, even unwillingly? How is it he could die alone, with only his pigeons to keep his company? A man who could shake buildings and project radio transmissions through the planet if one would give him the millions to work it... not even needing 1,000 trials... could not even obtain the patronage of his former employer worth \$1.2 billion in today's money.

For now and only for now we must assume that the problem has to do with the direction of the MIMS. In short, if the key in our first analyses was to use the diagram of #64 Before Completion, then Tesla's case may have been his inability to escape #63, After Completion:

63. Chi Chi / After Completion

above K'AN / THE ABYSMAL, WATER

below LI / THE CLINGING, FIRE

*This hexagram is the evolution of T'ai PEACE (11). The transition from confusion to order is completed, and everything is in its proper place even in particulars. The strong lines are in the strong places, the weak lines in the weak places. This is a very favorable outlook, **yet it gives reason for thought**. For it is just when perfect equilibrium has been reached that any movement may **cause order to revert to disorder**. The one strong line that has moved to the top, thus effecting complete order in details, is followed by the other lines. Each moving according to its nature, and thus suddenly there arises again the hexagram P'i, STANDSTILL (12). Hence the present hexagram indicates the conditions of a time of climax, which necessitate the utmost caution.*

THE JUDGMENT

AFTER COMPLETION. Success in small matters.

Perseverance furthers.

At the beginning good fortune.

At the end disorder.

*The transition from the old to the new time is already accomplished. In principle, everything stands systematized, and it is only in regard to details that success is still to be achieved. In respect to this, however, we must be careful to maintain the right attitude. Everything proceeds as if of its own accord, and this can all too easily tempt us to relax and let things take their course without troubling over details. Such **indifference is the root of all evil**. Symptoms of decay are bound to be the result. Here we have the rule indicating the usual course of history. But this rule is not an inescapable law. **He who understands it is in position to avoid its effects by dint of unremitting perseverance and caution.***

⁴⁰ MIMS 1.0, pp. 23

THE IMAGE

Water over fire: the image of the condition

In AFTER COMPLETION.

Thus the superior man

Takes thought of misfortune

And arms himself against it in advance.

*When water in a kettle hangs over fire, the two elements stand in relation and thus generate energy (cf. the production of steam). But the **resulting tension demands caution**. If the water boils over, the **fire is extinguished and its energy is lost**. If the heat is too great, the water evaporates into the air. These elements here brought into relation and **thus generating energy are by nature hostile to each other. Only the most extreme caution can prevent damage**. In life too there are junctures when all forces are in balance and work in harmony, so that everything seems to be in the best of order. In such times only the sage recognizes the moments that bode danger and knows how to banish it **by means of timely precautions**.⁴¹*

From this we can propose partially what happened to Nikola Tesla from a MIMS context. While he had more of a grip on the PEMF than anyone since “Thor”, he was indifferent. Famously he tore up his patents to help Westinghouse. He was not prepared with a lawyer to make new contracts. He was completely indifferent to money. He trusted the meaning and honor of the action of tearing up the patents that Westinghouse would shower him with the wealth until the end of his days. This was only partially true. Please note that the words tension and energy are absolutely vital in understanding this warning. Because Tesla stuck to the PEMF alone, and **did not understand the inversion - we are hypothesizing - between the *F* and *N* or *P* powers. (II)** He was unable to recognize that the power in business - a MIMS animal all to itself of completely unique sets of *P* principles and governed, in many ways differently by the *L/G* powers - was inverted to the equation of power in physics. There is no doubt that he felt damaged by this. He was frustrated with the US government for its failure to listen to and hire him. He was snubbed out of the Manhattan Project, and he was in fact lonely as he wrote in his own autobiography.

This is a tragedy of conditions that no businessman finds acceptable. Quite oppositely: most would rather have the awards and accomplishments and accolades, women, family, and success than be the wielder of such great power and knowledge and wisdom, and have nowhere to put it.

While both Edison and Tesla get accolades today, with the latter having an electric car named for him, it is clear that Edison had the results we should want. That is even despite him being the creator of the Electric Chair and having snubbed Tesla of \$50,000 (allegedly)... which would normally be considered “bad karma” by conventional wisdom. If it was, it doesn’t show in the record. He is beloved despite all... for giving us the light bulb.

Can business really do all of that? What else is revealed, in the dark or the light, in the MIMS that can give us some clue as to the nature of reality, and the “benefits of Heaven” aka luck, fortune, destiny, and the invisible rain that comes due out of what most call “spirit” and we simply call the *A* power: aether. How is the “charge of the divine” to be attracted, accumulated, and spun with the effortlessness of an AC generator, and the cavitation power of a mantis-shrimp punch? What MIMS exists, for the businessman, inventor, engineer, visionary, entrepreneur, investor, or others wishing for power, current, and capacitance? Let us venture into the dark aisles of Mysticism.⁴²

⁴¹ http://www.pantherwebworks.com/i_ching/bk1h53-64.html#63

⁴² Keep expectations low, for this paper, because discussion of the chakras, and electricity, will have to come in later, more detailed 2.2 papers.

2.2 The Mystique of Mysterious Mystics Moving in the Myst

Mystics, and mysticism, seem to get a bum rap. For that matter so does metaphysics although every scientist and mathematician engages in “side bits” of physics, especially those engaging to create pseudoscientific theories (mostly infallible or impossible to prove ones) such as: Dark Matter, Dark Energy, String Theory, Dark Photons⁴³, Fluffy Darkinos, black holes everywhere⁴⁴, times before the Big Bang⁴⁵, etc. For a working definition of mysticism in this EPEMC context, let’s consult the textbook definition, and contrast with superstition:

“mys·ti·cism

/ˈmɪstəˌsɪzəm/

noun

1. 1.
belief that union with or absorption into the Deity or the absolute, or the spiritual apprehension of knowledge inaccessible to the intellect, may be attained through contemplation and self-surrender.
"St. Theresa's writings were part of the tradition of Christian mysticism"
2. 2.
belief characterized by self-delusion or dreamy confusion of thought, especially when based on the assumption of occult qualities or mysterious agencies.
"there is a hint of New Age mysticism in the show's title"

su·per·sti·tion

/ˌsoʊpərˈstiʃ(ə)n/

noun

1. excessively credulous belief in and reverence for supernatural beings.
"he dismissed the ghost stories as mere superstition"
2. **Similar:** unfounded belief, credulity, magic, sorcery, witchcraft, fallacy, delusion, illusion
3. **Opposite:** science
 - a widely held but unjustified belief in supernatural causation leading to certain consequences of an action or event, or a practice based on such a belief.
 plural noun: **superstitions**
 "she touched her locket for luck, a superstition she had had since childhood"

⁴³

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329629284_Pseudoscience_Cannot_Be_Dark_Matter_A_Short_Concise_Rebuttal_to_Negative_Mass_Dark_Photons_and_the_General_Bunkish_Trend_Physics_in_Crisis_Must_be_Guided_to_Safe_Shores

⁴⁴ <https://www.livescience.com/fluffy-ball-darkinos-center-milky-way.html>

⁴⁵

<https://astronomy.com/news/2020/07/is-planet-nine-a-black-hole-or-a-planet-harvard-scientists-suggest-a-way-to-find-out#:~:text=The%20researchers%20proposed%20that%20the,holes%3A%20a%20primordial%20black%20hole.>

Looking at these two definitions, it isn't hard to see why mystics get a bad name, although both Sir Isaac Newton and Nikola Tesla - the two greatest scientific minds of world history - were both avid mystics. Newton was indeed an alchemist, although not of the John Dee variety.

Figure 4 - Harry Potter vs. Voldemort, credit: Warner Brothers

Note that even if energy source were not an issue⁴⁶, this would be plasma connecting them (clearly). All opinions on lightsabers so far have been the same conclusion.⁴⁷

The problem is that mysticism touches the deity through spirit, or has "occult qualities" or "mysterious agencies" and this touches near to what most people *think* magic is. The subject of

the arcane pseudosciences of magick (or magik) and of prestidigitonium (and illusionism) of recreational magic are not the subject of this paper. But suffice it to say, people conflate mysticism with something akin to Harry Potterism or Jediism. This may happen, on account of some venn diagrams of interests and subjects. But the fact is that "mysterious agencies" has been the perfect definition for Plasma-electromagnetism for well over 2,000 years, maybe over 5,000. PEMC appears to have gotten its start with the original Egyptians. Their followers certainly were occultists, obsessed with death and mummies, etc. But actually there were never any mummified remains found in the Great Pyramid, and it appears wholly the work of an arcane PEMC science based around MASERs, chemistry, plasma, and electric field generation⁴⁸. In fact, Kristian Birkeland made much study at the 30 degree latitude at Giza because his own terrella experiments indicated that is where plasma would tend to reconverge.

Figure 5 - Birkeland's terella⁴⁹ and the 30° N latitude filaments; credit: Birkeland/Peratt

12.4 Birkeland's Terrella Experiments

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Fig. 12.12 Birkeland's 8-cm globe. (Left): Experiment parameters adjusted such that the inflow-outflow currents are visible. (Right): Experiment parameters adjusted such that the ground or atmospheric currents are mostly visible

⁴⁶ Please note that even if this were possible in magick, it would kill the person.

⁴⁷ <https://www.iop.org/education/school-and-college-students/Qubit/Lightsabers>

⁴⁸ See Chris Dunn's work "Giza Power Plant"

⁴⁹ "12.5 Birkeland's trips to Egypt: Birkeland had done research in Egypt and Sudan in 1910, moving there in 1913 and remaining for nearly 3 years (Egeland and Burke 2005). The purpose reported was his interest in zodiacal light. There is reason to wonder if other observations of light in the laboratory raised his interest in this country lying at 30° N latitude as compared to Oslo at 70° N. Birkeland had spent much effort preparing a treatise that reportedly was nearly as complete as his earlier treatises." ~Dr. Peratt

Indeed, looking at the definition for mysticism there seems hardly any concern. Dreams are a biological, psychological, and medical scientific fact, and dreamy states are nothing new to marvel about. 2,800 years ago, Zhuangzi (Chuang Tzu) wrote,

“I was conscious only of my happiness as a butterfly, unaware that I was myself. Soon I awaked, and there I was, veritably myself again. Now I do not know whether I was then a man dreaming I was a butterfly, or whether I am now a butterfly, dreaming I am a man.”

This is a philosophical paper and that is a philosophical question not easily tackled by objective or materialistic-reductionistic sciences. Moreover, the only problem some scientists appear to have is with the concept of the Deity, but indeed it can be shown that there are at least 5 verifiable solutions to the existence vs. non-existence of God:

1. Yes, because of the filamented network of matter and energy, which is cyclical and self-contained, and continuously re-arranging
 - a. 1b: yes because the Big Bang was a moment of Creationism.
 - b. 1c: yes because the filamented structure shows self-organizing properties of neuronal structures indicating a kind of complexity-mediated structure akin to consciousness
2. Yes, because every culture around the world recorded a hermaphrodite fertility storm-god, identifiable as either an early but aged dwarf star, or Saturn, or later in middle-aged cultures Jupiter
 - a. 2b: yes because many middle to new aged cultures describe a Heracleian messiah, a son, who is a “new sun” based on a previous Heavenly Father and sent as a redeemer for #2
3. Yes, because there is a similarity of concept and data presence for the matrix [God] as [no-God] relying on the same (parameters); chiefly: omnipotence, infiniteness, immortality, omniscience, universal connection (usually love or sex)
4. Yes, because of the Dirac Delta mystical proof⁵⁰ which is essential to describing current

1. Dirac delta function

In the lecture it was discussed that the Dirac delta function $\delta(x)$ as a extremely peaked Lorentz or a Gauß curve. As an alternative show that for $n \rightarrow \infty$ we can use the following sequences of functions as a representation of the Dirac delta function.

a)

$$\delta_n(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & |x| < \frac{1}{n} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

b) $\delta_n(x) = np(nx)$, where the function $p(x)$ satisfies $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} p(x)dx = 1$

c) $\delta_n(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-n}^n e^{ixt} dt$

Hint: Given a test function $f(x)$ which is continuous at $x = 0$ and vanishes for $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$. Prove the filter property of the delta function: $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx f(x) \delta_n(x) = f(0)$. Use suitable substitutions to simplify the integrals and look up the definite integral $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^{-1} \sin t dt$

Figure 6 - Dirac Delta Function

⁵⁰ Mystical agency

5. Yes, because electromagnetism relies upon the imaginary number and waves cannot be describe with it
- a. 5b: yes because of irrational constants; both for irrationality and for constancy (tuning).

The first MIMS 1.0 paper dealt with “God” well enough for our EPEMC purposes⁵¹. The reality is that mostly what we care about is the movement of matter and energy.

As for mysticism, let’s see what kind of mystical research Newton and Tesla were into (Table 1). It could be said that there is a strong correlation here between the number of mystical studies, and overall success and fame. This is probably because more ideas = more bad ideas + more good ideas. The more ideas you have, the more hypotheses to work through, the more good results you will tend to get.

This leads us then to the next hypothesis:

It doesn’t matter if you study mysticism or avoid it, so long as you create sufficiently new ideas and new hypotheses to test. **The more trials, the more likely to hit upon good concrete evidence and concepts which will change the world.** (III)

What does all of this mean for our friends who want to bring the spiritual, imaginative, or ambitious into fruition? It means they need to be hungry. They need to innovate. So let’s talk about invention and innovation, and MIMS.

Table 1 - Mystical Studies of Well known Scientists

Sir Isaac Newton ⁵²	Nikola Tesla ⁵³	Galileo	Ed Leedskalnin
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Philosopher’s Stone ● The key aka Newton’s Clavis ● Temple of Solomon ● Prophecies (various) ● Atlantis ● Rosicrucianism ● Alchemy ● Mathematics ● Optics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scalar electricity ● Inner Alchemy ● Harmonics ● Free power / Opt ● “The white light” ● Destiny⁵⁴ ● Animal-human telepathy ● “Death beam”⁵⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Astrology⁵⁶ ● Various shapes of the Universe ● Horoscopes⁵⁷ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Magnetic Currents ● Relationship alchemy ● Sound levitation ● Numerology

⁵¹ Ibid. pp 5-6

⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Isaac_Newton%27s_occult_studies#2060

⁵³ <https://teslauniverse.com/nikola-tesla/articles/was-nikola-tesla-mystic>

⁵⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Nikola_Tesla_writings

⁵⁵ <https://www.history.com/news/9-things-you-may-not-know-about-nikola-tesla>

⁵⁶ <https://www.vox.com/2015/2/3/7969843/scientific-genius-magic>

⁵⁷ <https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-22105898>

2.3 Innovate, Don't Excuse

The author is now going to admit he has a serious philosophical problem with “professional skeptics.” From a scientific perspective, skepticism as a hobby is redundant. “Trust but verify” is an old axiom in politics⁵⁸, and it is apropos in science as well. Except mostly, you don't trust at all. You shouldn't trust anything the author writes without looking at the citations yourself. Therefore, why should you trust the minds of people who see little, and imagine less, producing almost nothing?⁵⁹

Put it another way: who would you rather go into business with, a man who makes notorious gaffes and mistakes like Elon Musk, or a scientific cultist and busybody like Michael Shermer? The answer is obvious. Mr. Shermer spends his energy in running publications which target people with new ideas. Over time, he frightens away young minds, and he rarely applies this healthy skepticism to CERN, black holes, and the like, and has a massive inherent bias for peer review journals, which are well known cultist cliques⁶⁰.

Figure 7 - Cybertruck Glass break

Whereas while Elon Musk trusts his cybertruck to have unbreakable glass and then is embarrassed when it doesn't, he doesn't tend to make that same mistake twice, and he gets far more done in the same period of time.

So now that we see that excessive skepticism is parading around as an excuse to prevent innovation, what are the parameters for innovation, and invention for that matter?

1. Challenge invisible orthodoxies⁶¹
2. Harness underappreciated trends⁶²
3. Leverage embedded competencies and assets
4. Address “unarticulated” needs
5. Use of comprehensive innovative metrics
 - a. Inputs
 - b. Throughputs
 - c. Outputs
 - d. Efficiency
6. Effective management
 - a. Leadership (measurable)
 - b. Competence
 - c. Climate
 - d. Balance

⁵⁸ Russian: Доверяй, но проверяй; Trust, but verify https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trust,_but_verify

⁵⁹ Especially when they are so easily defeated and guilty of character assassination on a podcast <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tFIAFo78xoQ>

⁶⁰ <https://www.jasss.org/18/2/13.html>

⁶¹ <https://hbr.org/2015/04/the-5-requirements-of-a-truly-innovative-company>

⁶² Including Analytics itself.

-
- e. Accountability
 - f. Capability (adaptation)
 - 7. Systemic views
 - a. Macro vs. micro vs. homeostasis vs. dynamics
 - 8. Novelty (or newness)
 - a. Niche
 - b. Evolutionary

All of these things, and not only these things, describe innovation and invention. They also describe MIMS particularly well. Please note, though, that we are most interested in the fifth item... the use of the *N* power in metrics or *analytics* as it is called in Operations Research.

It may be that really great CEOs and inventors, etc. have run mega companies and been successful on gut alone⁶³... but we also see in the case of Nikola Tesla and his dwindling relationships with powerhouses Westinghouse and JP Morgan, that actually these qualities were anti-mimsical. If anything, his intuition made people suspicious, and the lack of fore-metrics and data made his ideas difficult to sell. Though, it seems the US government had lots of ideas of how to put them to use as the 20th century rolled forward.⁶⁴

So what use is it then to be a mystic, and an inventor, if you do not fully utilize the Power of Numbers? It seems that you're more likely to be a success as a numerologist. Yet, there is something real to the concrete form of an invention, or to the increase in stock prices due to innovation. When an entrepreneur or engineer⁶⁵ sets out to innovate, they do so first from a place of inspiration, and usually that source is "the mother of all invention": necessity.

Why provide excuses for lack of innovation? Why say "one cannot create an overunity device"? Strictly speaking one may not violate the laws of thermodynamics, but since energy and power are everywhere, only needing direction (channel) and gradient (pressure) is required to create a flux of them. Then the issue isn't thermodynamic but just dynamical. It might be mechanical, chemical, electrical, digital... but in the end the products which are achieved by innovation are themselves often "over unity" as in they are worth more than the products that went into making them.

Facebook is a powerful software, but taking away the algorithms, actually it is fairly straightforward. However the use of the data collection and analytics is far more valuable. Google ads are more valuable than searches, and analytics are more valuable than ads and indeed improve the ads. When the inventors of Google's algorithm came up with their idea⁶⁶, they simply wanted to improve search results.⁶⁷ They had no ideas about email provision, ad software, analytics, etc. It was a pure invention for a pure reason. At that time their motto was, "Don't be evil." They no longer run the company, but the product continues to be a compounded return for the remainder of the company and many millions of others, because of the potency of the MIMS in question. "How can I get better search results?" Easy: data and relevance (competency by another name). As it happens though, their solution created exponential computing power output and throughput, and this, too, was inherently valuable. Value was created by the MIMS and the mimsical process itself! Innovation is the primary reason why war, genocide, and abortion are bad ideas in and of themselves:

⁶³ Paul J. Getty comes to mind.

⁶⁴ Robots, AI, intercontinental missiles, atomic bomb, etc.

⁶⁵ Energy, electricity, enthusiasm (god within), ... all start with e. How unique.

⁶⁶ <https://science.howstuffworks.com/innovation/inventions/who-invented-google.htm>

⁶⁷ <https://www.thoughtco.com/who-invented-google-1991852>

they reduce the total human energy value and potential for new ideas and invention. They are zero-sum-games.⁶⁸

Hypothesis: **Use metrics and analytics and look for more means to innovate, not less. (IV)**

Perhaps in another paper the remainder of these innovation concepts can be more readily explored.

2.4 The New Boss... Same as the Old Boss

The New World Order has been described as the following things by different persons:

- ★ The Changing World Order - Ray Dalio⁶⁹ (billionaire)
- ★ The Chinese Capitalism with Communist characteristics⁷⁰
- ★ The Bilderberg group⁷¹ and Bohemian Grove⁷² attendees
- ★ The Deep State⁷³
 - Council on Foreign Relations⁷⁴
 - FBI⁷⁵
 - State Department⁷⁶
 - Democratic Socialists of America infiltration⁷⁷
 - The Intelligence Community⁷⁸
- ★ The CIA⁷⁹
 - Potentially Nazis⁸⁰
 - Potentially communists (soviets)⁸¹
- ★ The Federal Reserve⁸²
 - Rothschild Bank of England⁸³

⁶⁸ Abortion has long had an effect upon semi-socialist countries in Europe, and their population issues are very bad for the economy of the EU. But now this problem is spreading to the United States as well.

⁶⁹ <https://www.principles.com/the-changing-world-order>

⁷⁰ This is the honest way to say it. You typically hear "capitalism with Chinese characteristics." But China was capitalistic for a long time before the CCP ruined the economy.

⁷¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bilderberg_meeting

⁷² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T3ss30ym2Vs> &

https://www.amazon.com/Bohemian-Grove-Facts-Fiction/dp/1943591008/ref=sr_1_2?dchild=1&keywords=bohemian+grove+mark+dice&link_code=qs&qid=1627568889&sr=8-2

⁷³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Deep_state_in_the_United_States

⁷⁴ <https://www.cfr.org/>

⁷⁵ <https://www.investors.com/politics/editorials/deep-state-trump-crimes-russia/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.rt.com/usa/state-department-coverup-498/>

⁷⁷

<https://www.projectveritas.com/news/breaking-deep-state-unmasked-irs-officials-you-should-give-increased-scrutiny-to-conservative-groups-i-dont-give-a-st-if-that-is-a-crime/>

⁷⁸ <https://thenewamerican.com/alex-newman-intelligence-community-a-criminal-enterprise-behind-the-deep-state/>

⁷⁹ <https://nsarchive2.gwu.edu/NSAEBB/NSAEBB146/index.htm>

⁸⁰ <https://jacobinmag.com/2020/10/cia-brainwashing-program-mk-ultra-sidney-gottlieb>

⁸¹ <https://www.rbth.com/history/328310-russian-double-agents>

⁸² <https://www.facts-are-facts.com/news/the-federal-reserve-is-privately-owned>

⁸³ <https://www.explorebesttoday.com/about-reserves/who-owns-the-federal-reserve-rothschild.html>

- Rockefeller Foundation⁸⁴ and other bankster family cartels⁸⁵
- Political dynasties such as Obamas, Trumps, Bidens, Bushes, etc.⁸⁶
- ★ NGOs
 - Trilateral Commission⁸⁷
 - World Bank⁸⁸
 - International Monetary Fund⁸⁹
 - World Economic Forum⁹⁰
- ★ Russia and the former KGB resurgent⁹¹
- ★ Illuminati or freemasons⁹²
 - Skull and Bones⁹³ and other known secret societies that control elections
- ★ Secret aliens (plural) and alien bloodlines etc.⁹⁴

The existence of the NWO is not really in question since it was readily spoken about by David Rockefeller in 1991.⁹⁵ It was being called out, however, as early as President Eisenhower, and especially John F. Kennedy, in 1961.⁹⁶ But its shape, form, function, and indeed any semblance of organized cohesiveness had not been formed. It seems the only thing they all have in common is a presumption that democracy is a joke, and *you* (the reader) are not to be in charge in any shape or form. In the words of many, “the only color that matters is green, and those who don’t have it.” Others have said the golden rule is, “He who has the gold makes the rules.”⁹⁷ There’s nothing really new about this, not even in 4,000 years of imperialism, kingdoms, feudal economy, and capitalism or socialism.

So what makes conspiracies like this tick? What gives them power and profundity? They rely on four facts about life and humanity:

1. Humans want/desire and when they get together they conspire to fulfill these desires.
2. There are more conspiracies than theories to fit them all and explain “what happened.”

⁸⁴ <https://www.rockefellerfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/Getting-to-the-Global-Goals.pdf>

⁸⁵

<https://hannenabintuherland.com/usa/the-federal-reserve-cartel-the-eight-families-who-own-usa-dean-henderson-herland-report/>

⁸⁶ “Secret Empires,” P. Schweizer, 2019

⁸⁷

<https://www.washingtonpost.com/archive/lifestyle/1992/04/25/beware-the-trilateral-commission/59c48198-9479-4c80-a70a-a1518b5bcfff/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/home>

⁸⁹ <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO>

⁹⁰ <https://www.weforum.org/great-reset/>

⁹¹ <https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/06/27/catherine-belton-putin-people-book-review-kgb-russia-west/>

⁹² <https://www.history.com/news/secret-societies-freemasons-knights-templar>

⁹³ Please note that BOTH 2004 US Presidential candidates were S&B members.

<https://www.britannica.com/topic/Skull-and-Bones-Yale>

⁹⁴ <https://www.amazon.com/Ancient-Aliens-New-World-Order/dp/B071HDW79T>

⁹⁵ “We are grateful to the Washington Post, The New York Times, Time Magazine and other great publications whose directors have attended our meetings and respected their promises of discretion for almost forty years.

It would have been impossible for us to develop our plan for the world if we had been subjected to the lights of publicity during those years. But, the world is now more sophisticated and prepared to march towards a world government. The supranational sovereignty of an intellectual elite and world bankers is surely preferable to the national auto-determination practiced in past centuries.” David Rockefeller – 1991

⁹⁶ <https://www.rev.com/blog/transcripts/john-f-kennedy-secret-societies-speech-transcript>

⁹⁷ <https://quoteinvestigator.com/2015/01/11/has-gold/>

3. People look for patterns as a part of their biology⁹⁸ and often create complex explanations for simple criminal morphology: means, motive, and opportunity.
4. People always want to “get ahead.” Many don’t care who they have to step on to do so. Most people intuitively know this. Some do it as a form of “can’t beat em... join em.”

So what does this have to do with our MIMS? Namely, it is that the mind creates what it seeks. Or as the Buddha said, “what you think, you become.”⁹⁹ A person that is conspiratorial, yin of a sort, will produce real conspiracies or theories, and in either case, they are a substitution for the actual production of useful products and services. Put another way, conspiracies, and attendant theories, “gunk up” the machinery of the MIMS by either diluting the concentrative process, or literally subtracting resources (time, mental effort, money) from worthwhile innovations.

Then why do them? Why do such anti-mimsy MIMS exist? Mostly because mankind has not accepted mankind’s psychology, mankind’s mytho-history, and mankind’s perversions as being beyond mere perversions and aberrations but as actual functions of a biodynamic system.

Refer back to the last MIMS 2.3: efficiency was a key aspect. But when we see nature, we don’t see efficiency so much as liberal, often garish purpose. Complex mating dances, inefficient chloroplasts, excessive pollen releases, flamboyant colorations which attract predators as well as mates; all of these bely a facet of life that is escaping the typical engineer: inefficiency and waste are not wasted in nature.

Yet in our pursuit of a MIMSical apparatus, a hypothesis of penultimate use and utility to describe the innovation of unseen forces and powers (an almost mechanical conspiracy, if you will), we are trying to impose a certain kind of leverage through forced efficiency.

Think of it this way: the Panama Canal is highly efficient. But its functional life is - in the scheme of geology - rather short lived and synthetic. But the Mississippi River and others like it are inherently useful for thousands of years. It isn’t efficient... but it is powerful, useful, and long-lived.

Similarly, if a MIMS is too specific, it may suffer from an inability to “fly freely” (so it seems to the author.)

But the components of conspiracies and theories are changeable, repetitive, and endlessly energy absorbent. If they are energy absorbent, perhaps then that will have a use in MIMS? Or rather, at least, the antithesis of them may have a use of liberating stored energies within the person. Following up on “mind your own business” it could be said that **paying too much attention to what others do/say will cause a MIMS to lose focus and potency. (V)**

There’s a lot of folksy wisdom in that hypothesis, and not a lot of ease in testing it. One would need to look at a lot of products that did or did not make it past invention and marketing to the mainstream of sales, and then find out why. Out of the millions of “made for TV” products two that seem to have made it were Oxyclean and the George Foreman Grill. It seems, to the author at least, that the products found a narrative - a niche - and stuck with it until it was successful. Their formulas are perhaps different (one relied on a very famous name) but the results spoke for themselves. Could it be that the company’s sole focus upon a single product had a lot to do with it? Yes, it very well could.

In which case, look at the failures of massive news outlets like CNN or MSNBC which peddle numerous, confusing & contradictory, annoying (even condescending) conspiracy theories. They lose ratings and viewership to those who are much better at packaging a consistent conspiracy theory program, like

⁹⁸ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/05/180531114642.htm>

⁹⁹ Technically, ““Whatever a monk keeps pursuing with his thinking and pondering, that becomes the inclination of his awareness.” Majjhima Nikaya 19 <https://fakebuddhaquotes.com/what-you-think-you-become/>

Infowars' Alex Jones. Why? It might have to do with the sudden emergence of support for his theories over theirs, or their hamfistedness, or the politics. But it is a costly mistake on their part¹⁰⁰. And this is why it appears that a mimsical approach should a) include room for some meandering, some waste and b) should be focused upon a central theme or message. It needs to pander to the *L* power, or what might more scientifically be called "Universal Consciousness."¹⁰¹

2.5 Creating a MIMS, Working Personal Finances, and then Verifying a MIMS

When you go through traumatic experiences, such as the COVID lockdown, it may be that engaging in excessive conspiracy speculation, or watching others like CNN do so, will provide some coping mechanism. However, the author's experience is that creating tools or looking for new resources to explain the unexplained and shed light onto dark crevices of one's knowledge will be better. The author tracked WHO data¹⁰², and spent time debunking various 5G COVID conspiracies¹⁰³ and myths. It revealed far more interesting connections between plagues and comets.

But from a personal financial survival standpoint, it led to the innovation of a more specific tool: the financial velocity tracker. The use of this MIMS as a tool was to first: move closer to the metrics idea and to utilize the power of Numbers. Second, to keep one's focus upon the business and upon survival, rather than upon various distractions.

Some of the tools of compensation by the author were not so successful. But this MIMS was fairly successful. In 2021, the author kept the tool in use, and has been able to start engaging in new forms of analytics in personal and business finance, that are not commonly done on the small business level. While the Management Accountability Plan and One Page Strategic Plan and Resiliency Plans were abandoned, the Financial Velocity tool was and remains in use precisely because it relies upon one of the powers. Why? Let's see what some examples of them yields:

¹⁰⁰

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/markjoyella/2021/06/29/cnn-drops-68-in-prime-as-fox-news-channel-crushes-competition-in-2q-cable-news-ratings/>

¹⁰¹ <https://courses.seas.harvard.edu/climate/eli/Courses/EP281r/Sources/Gaia/Gaia-hypothesis-wikipedia.pdf>

¹⁰² <https://bit.ly/2JFJGSw>

¹⁰³

https://www.academia.edu/43190878/OPINION_On_Gurus_Electric_Universe_Predictions_Bio_electrics_Comets_5G_and_Futurism

Figure 8 - 2020 Post COVID PPP injection and business performance

The injection of PPP in early May 2020 is obvious. The decline in All Cash as that is used is also obvious. But the subsequent rise afterwards is non-linear. It “does not follow” that during the late June and July period that there should automatically be an improvement in cash assets. Looking at the history, it looks like long term liabilities increased, and produced a bubble. Problems in short term liabilities seemed to increase in volatility as spending was (the author can confirm) high at the end of year. So what happened in 2021, as the tool was enhanced?

Figure 9 - 2021 Financial Velocity (log scale)

Please note: the primary decline post May 13 is directly proportional to the cryptocurrency downturn.

But now, running the business as a “profit first” to achieve a business’ function as a MIMS as opposed to making it a job (GAPP run), one should look at the weekly profits:

Figure 10 - Weekly Profits¹⁰⁴

Note the harmonic shape, known as an amplitude modulated signal¹⁰⁵.

What causes this? Boom and bust cycles? Spending cycles? Seasonality? It isn’t clear. But it does enable us to make predictions, such as the

compression felt this week. And yet, it also provides a peace of mind that (hypothetically) there will be an amplitudinal shift in currency in the following quarter.

Can we test this? Yes. And it will be tested, though the results may not show up here.

The point is that any MIMS should perform. **If a MIMS does not perform, it is not mediating the motion from spiritual to material and vice versa (VI)**. In such a case, what use is the MIMS, be it a business, or a tool, or a theory (conspiracy or otherwise)?

By this logic, if characters like David Icke or Alex Jones can make financial progress and “MYOB” even with theories - useless or not - then there is an inherent systemic value on display and the MIMS is functional. If they cannot, then there is a problem, probably with biases in the functional diagrams. There could, of course be problems in innovation and adhering to the edges of chaos¹⁰⁶ and novelty, but that’s all non-linear mathematics and not the author’s forte nor the subject of the paper. The non-linear dynamics must be minded, as well of course, but not at the expense of the obvious linear dynamics; in this case: the “bottom line.”

The point isn’t to show off (or complain) about the author’s business. It’s to demonstrate the inherent value of the power of numbers in what’s called “fundamental analysis”. That the MIMS behaves in this way has enabled stock brokers and many other investors to make investment decisions for hundreds of years without always having to know the “technical analysis” of a particular instrument. This is pretty useful. Many studies are pre-loaded onto softwares for this particular purpose!

The author now asks another question, and it seems only proper to bring it up here... but does it seem possible that all innovation is a form of amplitude modulated am signals? A sort of anti-damping curve?

¹⁰⁴ Note the first spike is another PPP injection, and it followed lag due to winter ice storms. Not causation, but correlation in “business signal.”

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.electronicshub.org/modulation-and-different-types-of-modulation/>

¹⁰⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Edge_of_chaos

Figure 11 - anti-damping... how human social innovation is progressing? Or are there amplitude modulators in there as well? Credit: author

The point is as we explore different MIMS scenarios, questioning “why did he succeed/get famous/wealthy?” or “why did that project/society/campaign fail?” or “how can we pre-plan for success and mitigate losses?” that we open ourselves to the need to move beyond pure philosophy and pure science and pure mathematics into a syncretic approach that uses all the 5 (or 6) powers. We should not forget the usefulness of the MIMS diagram either in design (hypothesis 0?) from the first paper, and we put new hypotheses about the MIMS to the test in real life scenarios. We must look for pragmatic explanations and results. Reification in internal and external alchemy is all about the reality and concreteness of form in the functional coming to life. For 150 years or more mankind has steadily increased these successful reifications of form. There is a definite increase in form with the locomotive, and then the automobile, airplane, battleship, television, microchip, radio, phone, cell phone, smart phone, etc. How many gaps are missing this reification because of the narrowness of focus? How many also fail to come to form for lack of concentration or for lack of proper process?

Conclusions

The MIMS is not at all clarified *but* there are several useful hypotheses that come from a loose philosophical analysis (that was done on the fly), and which warrant some form of testing in an engineering or Operations Research capacity:

- I. Use the scientific method and contain the infinite and the definite.
- II. There may exist an unknown inversion of behavior property in moderating the F and N powers - the Force and Numbers, respectively.
- III. The more trials of the system the more likely the system is to hit upon good, actionable data and results.
- IV. Use metrics and analytics and look for more means to innovate, not less
- V. paying too much attention to what others do/say will cause a MIMS to lose focus and potency (Distraction hypothesis)
- VI. If a MIMS does not perform, it is not mediating the motion from spiritual to material and vice versa¹⁰⁷

An astute analyst and reader will probably be able to find more hypotheses in each of these. But for shortening purposes, the author is proposing that followup papers explore 2.0 to 2.5 in separate papers, etc. More hypotheses and rigor for the current hypotheses could be done on each of these.

¹⁰⁷ This is an Operations research (and therefore “Tough Minded Management” <https://bit.ly/3BPDIZ2>) axiom as well.

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